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Synthesis and Characterization of Binuclear Schiff Base Copper(II) Complexes Derived From Acyclic End-Off Ligands: Spectral, Electrochemical and Computational Studies

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Abstract:

Acyclic hydroxo bridged binuclear copper(II) complexes of the formula $[Cu_2(L^{1-3})(NCS)_2(OH)]$ (**1a-1c**) have been synthesized in situ from phenol based binucleating pentadentate macro-acyclic compartmental “end-off” type Schiff base ligands, viz., 2,6-bis{N-[3-(methylamino)propyl]iminomethyl}-4-methylphenol(L^1), 2,6-bis{N-[3-(dimethylamino)propyl]iminomethyl}-4-methylphenol(L^2), 2,6-bis{N-[3-(diethylamino)propyl]iminomethyl}-4-methylphenol(L^3). The complexes are characterized by IR, UV-Vis, Single crystal X-Ray diffraction, emission and electrochemical studies. The UV-Visible spectrum of complex **1b** shows a dramatic red shift of the d-d transition band when compared to that of **1a** and **1c** due to high distortion in the geometry of the complex. All the complexes exhibit quasi-reversible one electron redox processes ($Cu^{II}Cu^{II} \xrightleftharpoons{e^-} Cu^{II}Cu^I \xrightleftharpoons{e^-} Cu^ICu^I$) at highly negative potentials ($E_{pc}^1 = -0.519$ to -0.543 V, $E_{pc}^2 = -1.282$ to -1.357 V). Density Functional Theory (DFT) calculations support the spectral study on the effect of distortion around the metal centres, electronic and electrochemical properties of the complexes.

Key words: Binuclear “End-off” Copper(II) Complexes, Alkyl substituents, Electrochemical Studies, DFT Studies.

1. Introduction

Over the past few decades, a great deal of investigations on the synthesis and characterization of various binuclear copper complexes has been reported owing to their noteworthy significance in the characteristic magnetic properties, charge separation, multi electron transfer process and electron transport.¹ The binuclear complexes serve as models in mimicking and studying the structure and nature of various enzymes and metalloproteins in biological systems such as tyrosinase, hemocyanines, blue oxidases, catechol oxidases, etc.² This is because the multi metal centres in these enzymes possess several properties such as antiferromagnetism and EPR inactivity similar to binuclear copper complexes. Knowledge on the mechanism of exchange interaction between the paramagnetic metal centres, has led to the designing of novel magnetic materials using suitable building units.³ Binuclear metal complexes can serve as receptors for small substrate molecules such as NO which is a gaseous, short-living species. It is an important signaling molecule and is known to involve in various functions such as vasodilatation, killing of cancerous and microbial cells, neurotransmission, etc.^{4,5} Cooperative effect of the two metal centres plays a major role in assembling the substrate molecules. Binuclear “end-off” complexes find applications as synthetic biomimetic devices,⁶ catalysts,⁷ antimicrobial agents,⁸ DNA binding and cleaving agents,⁹ corrosion inhibitors,¹⁰ and fluorescent probes.¹¹

Phenoxo bridged copper(II) complexes serve not only as bioinorganic models in enzymatic reactions but also catalyzes synthetic oxidation reactions.^{12,13} Krebs et al., showed that “end-off” type complexes with exogenous –OH bridging anions act as highly active catalysts in the oxidation of catechol.¹⁴ The choice of suitable bridging anion also helps to tune the ability of the binuclear copper complexes to act as potential homogenous catalysts.

The symmetric “end-off” compartmental ligands are often prepared by a single step condensation of diformyl precursors and appropriate diamines. The corresponding complexes are synthesized by template or stepwise procedures, and are found to have a bridging endogenous phenolate oxygen with either one or two of the exogenous bridging groups, viz., CH₃COO⁻, OH⁻, N₃⁻, Cl⁻, Br⁻, or OCN⁻.¹⁵ Such designs lead to enforced ideal distances between the donor sites and the endogenous bridges which result in better coordination environments when compared to the complexes derived from macrocyclic and side-off ligands.¹⁶ This is because such systems do not favour the formation of exogenous bridges due to the small distance between the bimetal centres leading to rigid and restricted coordination geometries.^{17,18} It has been shown that the competitive and co-operative role played by the bridging anion and the phenoxide group is important in the construction of these types of complexes.¹⁹

It is interesting to understand the degree of distortion around the Cu(II) metal centres due to the presence of various alkyl substituents present on the nitrogen donor atoms of the ligands and the structural, electronic and electrochemical behavior of the complexes **1a-1c**. In this paper, the synthesis, spectroscopy, electrochemical and computational studies of a series of acyclic “end-off” binuclear Cu(II) complexes derived from symmetric Schiff base ligands (**L**¹, **L**² and **L**³) are reported in order to provide insight into their potential as new transition metal probes which may find applications in various fields. The experimental observations support the theoretical work carried out.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

2,6-Diformyl-4-methylphenol was prepared as per the literature method.²⁰ Copper(II) nitrate trihydrate (AR), sodium thiocyanate (AR), acetonitrile (AR), dimethyl formamide (AR) and dimethyl sulfoxide (AR) were obtained from Merck. Absolute methanol was purchased from commercial source and was used as received. *N*-Methyl-1,3-diaminopropane (AR), 3-(dimethylamino)-1-propylamine (AR) and 3-(diethylamino)-1-propylamine (AR) were procured from Sigma Aldrich. Tetra(n-butyl) ammonium perchlorate (TBAP) was purchased from Fluka and recrystallized from hot methanol. (Caution! TBAP is potentially explosive; hence, care should be taken while handling).

2.2. Physical methods

Elemental analyses for the complexes were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 Series CHNS/O Analyzer. IR spectra were recorded using a Bruker TENSOR FT-IR spectrometer in the range 4000-650 cm⁻¹ as KBr pellets. Electronic spectra were recorded on a JASCO V-530 spectrophotometer in the range 200-800 nm using 10 μM samples in methanol. Emission intensity measurements were carried out on a Horiba-Jobin Yvon FluoroMax-4P spectrofluorimeter. Electrochemical measurements of the samples were carried out at room temperature using a CHI1200B electrochemical analyzer. A standard three electrode cell was employed in which Ag/AgCl/KCl electrode was used as the reference electrode, Pt electrode was used as the counter electrode and Glassy carbon electrode was used as the working electrode. TBAP was used as the supporting electrolyte (0.1 M) and the concentration of all the solutions in DMF were around 10⁻³M. The samples were deaerated prior to the measurements.

2.3. Synthesis of binuclear copper(II) complexes

2.3.1. [Cu₂(L¹)(NCS)₂(OH)] (**1a**)

2,6-Diformyl-4-methylphenol (0.164 g, 1 mmol) in methanol was slowly added to a solution of *N*-methyl-1,3-diaminopropane (0.205 mL, 2 mmol) in 5 mL of methanol and stirred for 30 minutes. The resulting mixture was refluxed for 10 minutes. To the yellow solution obtained, copper(II) nitrate trihydrate (0.485 g, 2 mmol) was added and refluxed for another 30 minutes. The addition of sodium thiocyanate (0.162 g, 2 mmol) resulted in the

precipitation of green coloured microcrystals. (**Scheme 1**) Yield: (0.45 g, 80%). Found: C, 40.50; H, 5.10; N, 14.96. Calc. for $C_{19}H_{28}N_6O_2S_2Cu_2$: C, 40.48; H, 5.01; N, 14.91%. UV-Vis [$\lambda_{max}(\text{DMF})/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/M^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$): 275(32500), 415(10100), 637(60). Selected FT-IR (KBr Disc, ν/cm^{-1}): 1635s (C=N), 2071s (SCN).

Complexes $[Cu_2(L^2)(NCS)_2(OH)]$ (**1b**) and $[Cu_2(L^3)(NCS)_2(OH)]$ (**1c**) were synthesized following the above procedure, by varying the diamines viz., 3-(Dimethylamino)-1-propylamine (0.25 mL, 2.0 mmol) and 3-(diethylamino)-1-propylamine (0.315 mL, 2 mmol) respectively.

2.3.2. $[Cu_2(L^2)(NCS)_2(OH)]$ (**1b**)

Colour: Light green microcrystals. Single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction were obtained by recrystallization of the complex **1b** from acetonitrile. Yield: (0.48 g, 81%). Found: C, 42.59; H, 5.32; N, 14.60. Calc. for $C_{21}H_{32}N_6O_2S_2Cu_2$: C, 42.62; H, 5.45; N, 14.20%. UV-Vis [$\lambda_{max}(\text{DMF})/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/M^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$): 256 (267400), 370(59400), 708(271). Selected FT-IR (KBr Disc, ν/cm^{-1}): 1636s (C=N), 2088s (SCN).

2.3.3. $[Cu_2(L^3)(NCS)_2(OH)]$ (**1c**)

Colour: Dark green solid. Yield: (0.51 g, 79%). Found: C, 46.61; H, 5.70; N, 13.0. Calc. for $C_{25}H_{37}N_6O_2S_2Cu_2$: C, 46.57; H, 5.78; N, 13.03%. UV-Vis [$\lambda_{max}(\text{DMF})/\text{nm}$ ($\epsilon/M^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$): 258(117300), 371(29300), 648(121). Selected FT-IR (KBr Disc, ν/cm^{-1}): 1640s (C=N), 2096s (SCN).

Scheme 1: Synthesis of $[Cu_2(L^{1-3})(NCS)_2(OH)]$ complexes

2.4. Computational studies

All calculations were performed at the Density Functional level (DFT) of theory employing Gaussian 09 (G09) program package.²¹ The ground state geometries of the ligands and their corresponding complexes were fully optimized in the gas phase without imposing any symmetry constraints combining Becke's three parameter hybrid exchange functional with the gradient corrected correlation functional of Lee-Yang-Parr (B3LYP).^{22,23} Frequency calculations were performed using the same basis set, which assured that all the optimized structures correspond to real minima and no imaginary frequency. The standard basis set of atomic functions, LanL2Dz (Los Alamos double- ζ) was applied for geometry optimization.²⁴

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Synthesis

All attempts to isolate the free Schiff-base ligands resulted in the formation of orange oil. Therefore, binuclear copper(II) complexes (**1a-1c**) bearing hydroxide bridging groups were synthesized *in situ* by the reaction of stoichiometric ratio of the starting material 2, 6-Diformyl-4-methyl phenol, an appropriate diamine and copper(II)

nitrate trihydrate in methanol medium as shown in **Scheme 1**. All the complexes are stable in air and are soluble in acetonitrile, DMF, DMSO. The complex **1b** was crystallized as dark green rectangle shaped crystals.

3.2. Characterization of binuclear copper(II) complexes (1a-1c)

3.2.1. IR and electronic spectra of the binuclear copper(II) complexes (1a-1c)

The FT-IR spectra of complexes (**1a-1c**) are shown in **Fig. 1**. All the complexes show an absorption band around $3460\text{-}3600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ characteristic of the $\nu(\text{O-H})$ mode of bridging hydroxo group.²⁵ A peak around 1636 cm^{-1} is indicative of the formation of $\text{C}=\text{N}$ by Schiff base condensation. Complex **1a** displays one broad peak at $\sim 3195\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibration. This is absent in the case of the complexes **1b** and **1c** as both the nitrogen donor atoms in these complexes are fully saturated with alkyl substituents. The bands in the region $1520\text{-}1560\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the complexes **1a-1c** suggest the presence of phenoxide bridging with the metal ions. All the complexes display a distinct $\nu(\text{CN})$ mode for the NCS^- group at 2073 cm^{-1} .²⁶

Fig. 1. FT-IR Spectra of the complexes $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1a**), $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1b**) and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1c**).

Fig. 2. UV-Vis Spectra of the complexes $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1a**), $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1b**) and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1c**).

The UV-Vis absorption spectra of the complexes were recorded in dimethylformamide (DMF) and the spectra of complexes (**1a-1c**) are shown in **Fig. 2**. The spectra reveal three main features: The intense peaks below 260 nm are due to the intraligand charge-transfer transitions associated with $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions involving molecular orbitals located primarily on the phenolate chromophore.²⁷ A peak in the range of 370-420 nm indicates phenolate to copper charge transfer transitions (LMCT).²⁸ The electronic spectra shown in the inset graph represents very weak d-d transitions in the visible range of 630-720 nm. This is consistent with Cu^{II} phenolate complexes possessing trigonal bipyramidal geometries.²⁹ The d-d transition of complex **1b** was found to occur at a longer wavelength (708 nm) when compared to **1a** and **1c**. This indicates a greater distortion in the co-ordination geometry compared to **1a** (637 nm) and **1c** (648 nm).³⁰ These compounds have almost identical coordination environment and show similarity in their energies. Therefore, the degree of distortion in these complexes follows the order **1a**<**1c**<**1b**.³¹

3.2.2. Emission studies

The emission spectra of the complexes **1a**, **1b** and **1c** and their corresponding ligands were examined at room temperature using DMF as the solvent. The concentration of the complexes used was 0.1mM. The spectra of the ligands and their respective complexes are shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. Emission spectra of (a) ligand **L¹** and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1a**), (b) ligand **L²** and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1b**) and (c) ligand **L³** and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1c**).

When excited at 415 nm, complex **1a** displayed an emission band at 501 nm with a red shift of about 51 nm relative to the emission band of the Ligand **L¹** (λ_{em} of **L¹**= 450 nm; λ_{exc} of **L¹**= 317 nm). Complex **1b** exhibits a broad emission band at 475 nm when excited at 370 nm with a blue shift of 33 nm relative to the emission band of the ligand **L²** (λ_{em} of **L²**= 508 nm; λ_{exc} of **L²**= 424 nm). When excited at 371 nm, complex **1c** displayed an emission band at 460 nm with a blue shift of 38 nm when compared to the emission band of the ligand **L³** (λ_{em} of **L³**= ~498 nm; λ_{exc} of **L³**= 433 nm). We tentatively assign these bands to LMCT transitions.

The emission of complex **1a** underwent a red shift whereas a blue shift was observed in the case of complexes **1b** and **1c**. The blue shift in complexes **1b** and **1c** may be due to weaker coordination between Cu and the N atoms of the ligand moiety. This is due to the steric hindrance imposed by the two methyl and ethyl substituents when compared to complex **1a** where one methyl group is attached to N3 and N4 donor atoms. Red shift in complex **1a**, results from a decrease in the ligand conformational rigidity.³² The blue shift in the emission maxima of the complexes **1b** and **1c** result from increase in the ligand conformational rigidity. This can also be correlated with the high energy absorption maxima of **1b** and **1c** observed in UV-Vis spectra.³⁴

In solution, the ligands could freely vibrate and rotate. This enables the rotational and vibrational relaxation modes of the non-radiative decay. As a consequence of complexation, the rigidity of the complex increases. This renders the non-radiative decay from the excited state less probable, leading to an enhancement in the emission intensity.³⁵ Literature suggests that the first row transition metals, viz., Cr, Mn, Fe, Co, Ni and Cu quench the fluorescence emission intensity via an electron or energy transfer between the metal and the fluorophore upon

coordination with the ligand.^{36,37} This explains the decrease in the emission intensity of the complexes (**1a-1c**) when compared to their respective ligands (**L¹-L³**). Similar types of complexes find application as luminescent probes for biological applications under physiological conditions.^{38,39}

3.2.4. Electrochemical Studies

The cyclic voltammograms (CV) of the complexes **1a** to **1c** are shown in **Fig. 4**. The electrochemical behavior of these complexes was studied in the potential range of 0 to -2 V by cyclic voltammetry in DMF containing 0.1 M TBAP as the supporting electrolyte. The redox potentials of these complexes are summarized in **Table 1**. The electrochemical data of the complexes indicate that these complexes undergo reduction at highly negative potentials. Each complex shows two quasi-reversible (one electron transfer) peaks within the potential range of -0.34 to -0.51 V for the first reduction potential and -1.03 to -1.36 V for the second reduction potential. The first and second redox processes correspond to the redox couples, Cu^{II}Cu^{II}/Cu^{II}Cu^I and Cu^{II}Cu^I/Cu^ICu^I respectively as shown below:

The relative stability of the mixed valent species Cu^{II}Cu^I in the equilibrium mixture of Cu^{II}Cu^{II} and Cu^{II}Cu^I has been calculated using the relationship $\log K_{\text{con}} = \Delta E / 0.0591$. The difference in the peak positions may substantiate the stability of the Cu^{II}Cu^I.⁴⁰ The larger the separation between the potentials of the first and second redox processes, the greater the stability of the mixed valence species or greater the exchange interaction with respect to the iso-valent species.⁴¹ It can be noted that the decrease in the peak separation between E¹_{1/2} and E²_{1/2} is reflected in the decrease in the K_{con} values of the complexes.⁴²

The decrease in the E_{1/2} value of the complex **1b** is due to the high distortion prevailing in the geometry of the complex. It is known that easy electrochemical reduction is more favoured, if the coordination geometry around the metal center is increasingly distorted.⁴³ The coordination site influences less than the effect of geometrical distortion on the redox potential of complexes. This was found to be in good agreement with the UV-Vis spectral results. As discussed earlier, the d-d transition in **1b** was found to occur at a longer wavelength (708 nm) when compared to the complexes **1a** (637 nm) and **1c** (648 nm). The longer the wavelength of d-d transition, the greater will be the distortion. The degree of distortion in the complexes is evidenced from the decrease in the E_{1/2} value as suggested by CV studies and UV-Visible spectra (red shift). This follows the order of distortion: **1a < 1c < 1b**.

The high peak separation observed between the reduction and the corresponding oxidation peaks in the range of 200-300 mV may be due to the stepwise reduction of the C=N bonds. This may be due to the transfer of electrons from the filled d orbital of the Cu(I) to the C=N linkage.⁴⁴ Usually the electronegative and hard nature of the phenoxide ligands influence the redox potentials of the complexes. The value of the cathodic current is larger than the anodic current which may be due to the probable structural reorganization of the copper coordination sphere due to solvation or chemical changes.⁴⁵

Table 1. Electrochemical data for the complexes in DMF.

Name of the Complex	E ¹ _{pc} V	E ¹ _{pa} V	E ¹ _{1/2} V	ΔE ¹ mV	E ² _{pc} V	E ² _{pa} V	E ² _{1/2} V	ΔE ² mV	K _{Con}
1a	-0.543	-0.334	-0.438	209	-1.357	-1.085	-1.221	272	1.773x10 ¹³
1b	-0.519	-0.338	-0.428	181	-1.282	-1.028	-1.155	254	2.001x10 ¹²
1c	-0.531	-0.343	-0.437	188	-1.327	-1.107	-1.217	220	1.578x10 ¹³

Potential V versus Ag/AgCl; Sweep rate 50 mV/sec; Supporting electrolyte: TBAP; ΔE_p=E_{pc} - E_{pa}; E_{1/2}=0.5(E_{pc} + E_{pa}) where E_{pc} and E_{pa} are the cathodic and anodic peak potentials respectively.

Fig. 4. Cyclic voltammograms of the complexes $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^1)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1a**), $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^2)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1b**) and $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L}^3)(\text{NCS})_2(\text{OH})]$ (**1c**)

3.2.5. Computational studies

The structures of all the three ligands and complexes were fully optimized by performing unrestricted DFT calculations. The calculated geometrical parameters are shown in **Table 2**.

Table 2. The selected bond distances and bond angles of the gas phase geometry optimized complexes.

Selected atoms	Bond distances (Å)		
	1a	1b	1c
Cu(1)-O(1)	2.11035	2.13333	2.12279
Cu(1)-O(11)	1.94267	1.93681	1.92134
Cu(1)-N(2)	1.98139	1.99281	2.00134
Cu(1)-N(3)	2.18787	2.28623	2.45313
Cu(1)-N(6)	2.08965	2.05702	2.02066
C(9)-N(2)	1.30487	1.30487	1.30267
Cu(2)-O(1)	2.09063	2.10278	2.12055
Cu(2)-O(11)	1.92947	1.91766	1.92116
Cu(2)-N(1)	2.00138	2.00206	2.00157
Cu(2)-N(4)	2.28659	2.36156	2.44895
Cu(2)-N(5)	2.02038	2.01687	2.02172
C(11)-N(1)	1.30281	1.30270	1.30268
Bond Angles (Degree)			
O(1)-Cu(1)-N(3)	130.51251	123.91669	114.77665
O(1)-Cu(1)-N(6)	134.80757	138.18949	151.28520
N(2)-Cu(1)-O(1)	88.96114	88.44981	88.23576
O(11)-Cu(1)-N(2)	164.66462	163.14045	163.07452
O(11)-Cu(1)-N(3)	91.46439	96.32396	102.79212
O(11)-Cu(1)-N(6)	92.75261	92.40004	94.35807
O(11)-Cu(1)-O(1)	75.86791	74.69095	75.28556
N(2)-Cu(1)-N(3)	96.85483	92.98702	87.45501
N(2)-Cu(1)-N(6)	99.67733	100.48043	98.47180
N(6)-Cu(1)-N(3)	92.66455	96.56166	93.48711

Cu(1)-O(1)-Cu(2)	97.57992	97.53549	97.13774
O(1)-Cu(2)-N(4)	112.38863	113.06378	115.03311
O(1)-Cu(2)-N(5)	151.39371	151.48789	151.21664
N(1)-Cu(2)-O(1)	88.10156	88.38310	88.24337
O(11)-Cu(2)-N(1)	164.59012	163.73562	163.16121
O(11)-Cu(2)-N(4)	98.68588	101.68274	102.58559
O(11)-Cu(2)-N(5)	93.10050	93.64603	94.44575
O(11)-Cu(2)-O(1)	76.61220	75.79834	75.34247
N(1)-Cu(2)-N(4)	88.83703	87.84529	87.60348
N(1)-Cu(2)-N(5)	99.59777	98.69402	98.35439
N(5)-Cu(2)-N(4)	95.38584	94.86608	93.30853
Cu(2)-O(11)-Cu(1)	109.41094	111.48501	111.77987

The reported experimental⁴⁶ and computed structures of complex **1b** are broadly similar and possess distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry around each metal centre. In complexes **1a**, **1b** and **1c**, Cu1 has a penta coordinate environment comprised of the bridging phenolate oxygen O1, N2 of the iminic pendant arm, N3 of the amine, N5 of the isothiocyanate group and O11 of the exogenous hydroxo group. Cu2 also is penta coordinate and bonded to the bridging phenolate oxygen O1, N1 of the iminic pendant arm, N4 of the amine, N6 of the isothiocyanate group and O11 of the exogenous hydroxo group. All the complexes retain a nearly coplanar μ -hydroxo- μ -phenolato dicopper(II) core. The bridging of copper(II) ions by phenolate oxygen results in distinct Cu1-O1 and Cu2-O1 bond distances. In all the three complexes, it can be seen that the distance between Cu2-O1 < Cu1-O1. The angles N1-Cu2-O11 and N1-Cu1-O11 in the calculated structures (**1a-1c**) are comparable to each other. *i.e.*, in **1a** they are 164.59012° and 164.66462°, in **1b** they are 163.73562° and 163.14045°, in **1c** they are 163.16121° and 163.07452° respectively. The sum of the angles between N5, O1 and N4 around Cu2, and N6, O1 and N3 around Cu1 is found to be around 359°. This substantiates the presence of distorted trigonal bipyramidal geometry around the Cu(II) metal centres. All the results discussed above are in good agreement with the experimental values in the case of complex **1b**.

It is also found that the iminic bonds between C11-N1 are shorter than between C9-N2 in all the complexes. The Cu1-N3 and Cu2-N4 bond lengths are greater when compared to those of Cu1-N2 and Cu2-N1 respectively. The Cu----Cu separation in complexes **1a**, **1b** and **1c** are 3.16042, 3.18580 and 3.18145Å respectively. This increase in the distance between the metal centres may be due to the extension of amino alkyl chains out of plane from the metal centres, dragging them apart from each other. The trend in the separation between the metal centres in complexes is as follows: **1a**<**1c**<**1b**. This strongly supports the distortion observed in the complexes through UV-Vis spectral studies and the trend (**1a**<**1c**<**1b**) observed in the stepwise electrochemical reduction of metal centres.

The optimized energies of HOMO and LUMO levels of the complexes are given in Table 3. Sharing of the negative charge of the ligand between the two metal centres leads to an increase in the energy gap between the frontier molecular orbitals of the complex. This can be correlated with the blue shift observed from the emission maxima for the complexes. The trend was found to be: **1a**<**1b**<**1c**. The same trend can be related to the increase in the rigidity of the complexes.

Table 3. Positions of HOMO and LUMO of complexes **1a**, **1b** and **1c**.

Name of the complex	LUMO (eV)	HOMO (eV)	$\Delta E = \text{LUMO} - \text{HOMO}$ (eV)
1a	-3.98	-5.15	1.17
1b	-4.02	-5.24	1.22
1c	-3.89	-5.32	1.43

A schematic representation of the frontier molecular orbitals of the complexes is shown in Fig. 5. DFT studies can also throw light on the redox behavior of the complex systems. It is known that when the electron density on Cu is less, reduction of Cu(II) to Cu(I) will occur at a less negative potential.⁴⁷ It is observed from the

HOMO in Fig. 5 that the electron density on Cu^{II}(2) atom is less in complex **1b** than in complexes **1a** and **1c**. This observation goes hand in hand with the experimental results where complex **1b** undergoes reduction at less negative potentials when compared to complexes **1a** and **1c**.

Fig. 5. HOMO and LUMO of complexes [Cu₂(L¹)(NCS)₂(OH)] (**1a**), [Cu₂(L²)(NCS)₂(OH)] (**1b**) and [Cu₂(L³)(NCS)₂(OH)] (**1c**).

From the above results, the following mechanism may be operative in bringing about the reduction of the metal centres owing to the high electron density over Cu2 when compared to Cu1 metal centre in **1a**, **1b** and **1c**. Cu2 atom gets reduced first followed by Cu1.

Other factors such as the basicity of the amine in solution, presence of trace amount of contaminants like water in the solvent used for analysis, antiferromagnetic coupling between the metal centres and/or the lower effective nuclear charge at the Cu center, or electronic or steric effects may induce different environments around the metal centres, which in turn can have a direct effect in altering the reduction potential.^{48,49}

4. Conclusions

Synthesis and characterization of a series of binuclear Cu(II) complexes using pentadentate ligands are reported. Spectral studies reveal the structural distortion around the metal centres in the complexes. The degree of distortion follows the order: **1a**<**1c**<**1b**. Upon introduction of bulky substituents in the amine moiety of the ligands,

the rigidity of the complexes is found to increase in the following order: **1a**<**1b**<**1c** due to an increase in the energy gap between HOMO and LUMO levels as suggested by emission and computational studies. The cyclic voltammogram of the complexes exhibit two quasi-reversible one electron transfer redox processes. viz., Cu^{II}Cu^{II}/Cu^ICu^I and Cu^{II}Cu^I/Cu^ICu^I redox couples. CV studies suggest that increase in the distortion of the complexes leads to easy reduction of the metal centres. These observations are further substantiated by DFT calculations according to which the copper centre with less electron density undergoes easy reduction from Cu(II) to Cu(I) state followed by the metal centre with more electron cloud.

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